

Green Marketing: A Strategy for Sustainable Development

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Abstract

Many companies nowadays want to incorporate greenness into their production system. The current available process and literature do not provide a solid framework to go toward total greenness. Hence, the paper tries to demonstrate a mission statement to capture the green value, and culture of the community and assemble everyone to become socially responsible. The society today we are residing in is continuously changing. In this domain of alteration, industrialization has played a role in transition within the society. It has converted our livelihood from an agrarian economy to an industrialized-based economy. Most of the human toll is replaced with an automated production system. In this course of development, some of the features of the environment get affected badly. This effect takes many forms and led to a negative influence on the land, water, and environment. The global effect of this pollution is becoming serious day by day, leading to sickness and death all over the world. It is in this framework that the concept of green marketing takes place.

KeyWords: Environment, green marketing, Industrialized-based economy

Introduction

Green marketing in general terms refers to the modernization and development of especially those products or services which are acknowledged to be ecologically safe and supportable. The approach of green marketing first came to notice during the era of the late 80s and 90s. The American Marketing Association (AMA) for the first time held a workshop on 'Ecological Marketing' in 1975. The main slogan of the workshop was 'sustainability in everyday activity. In 1987, a report was prepared by World Commission on environment and development which specifically mentioned that companies should focus on meeting the needs of the present generation without negotiating the needs of future generations. This report later came to be known as Brundtland Report and became another specific step toward green marketing. During the era of 90s that in 1992 and 1993 two famous books were published namely- 'Green Marketing' by Ken Peattie in the context of the United Kingdom (U.K) and 'Green Marketing: Challenges and Opportunities for New Marketing Age' by Jacquelyn Ottman in the context of United States (U.S) respectively, marked the first milestone of green marketing. According to these writers, the concept of green marketing should be incorporated into every step of marketing.

In India, the history of being 'Green' can be traced back to the era of the 60s. when the government of India launched a revolution in 1965 termed as 'Green Revolution' with the help

Literature Review

Today companies are representing their commitment to green marketing to meet their customers' expectations along with various

of M.S. Swaminathan. This revolution led to great success as it has changed the status of India from a food-deficit country to the world's leading agricultural country. Green Revolution has helped rapidly increase wheat and rice production and also brought varied improved fertilizers. Later in 1991, the government of India started a scheme called ECO MARK SCHEME, which laid the foundation for green marketing. Eco Mark is the label or certification by the Bureau of Indian Standard (BIS) given for those products which are tested and found ecologically safe or less harmful to the environment. Since 1991 a fundamental change in consumer preferences and lifestyle can be gauged. There is a jump from traditional marketing to green marketing, which brought many challenges for the companies. Nevertheless, green marketing has brought many changes in customers' attitudes, companies' competitive edge, technological innovations, advertisements, etc. Presently, Indian urban and semi-urban populations are becoming more and more aware of green products. Herbal-based products are now in huge demand. India's Ayurvedic Heritage is constantly approaching the importance of natural beauty products, healthy lifestyles such as yoga, and natural food consumption.

It incorporates a huge range of activities such as product modification, modified product packaging, use of recycled materials, etc. Therefore, green marketing can be described as a broad movement toward socially and environmentally conscious business practices (Fernando.J, 2021).

environmental, social, and governance (ESG) standards. Here, ESG refers to a set of standards upon which the company operates as a representative of mother nature and manages to

maintain relationships with employees, consumers, dealers, and the communities where the company is situated. Companies' governance on the other hand contracts with leadership, audits, executive pay, internal control, and shareholder rights (Scott. G, 2022). Hence, defining green marketing is somewhat little complicated due to various terms associated with it such as environmental marketing, ecological marketing, etc.

Green marketing, environmental marketing, sustainable marketing,eco-marketing, etc.,are part of today's new marketing approaches. These are the approaches that are not only focused or conscious of nature but also give stiff competition to already existing marketing methods and thinking direction and practices. The concept of green marketing is not only the usage of eco-friendly products or following eco-friendly policies but also acknowledging the customers about its usage and production process. With the increase in climate change and global warming, people whole over the **History of Green Marketing**

As obvious human needs are unlimited and the green marketing approach tries to make balance with nominal detrimental impact on the environment. Green marketing not only incorporates consumer or physical products but also includes the service sector. As both products and services contribute toward ecological balance. However, the role of the manufacturing sector is more significant as the process includes production, logistics, and selling, which build a huge toll upon the environment. Hence, green marketing creates balance by preparing stakeholders to take part in the process of social responsibility (Pranali. N, 2010).

Problem Statement

Purpose of the Study: The present paper describes the concept of green marketing, its importance, and recent trends of companies toward green marketing.

continent became more concerned about environmental problems compared to past decades. Presently, both businesses and customers started to challenge eco-friendly products as concern for health and sustainability dominates (FuiYeng. W &Yazdanifard. R, 2015).

From the above discussion it can be concluded that presently, the green marketing approach has become very popular. Due to the degrading nature of the environment, people are more concerned about doing things in such a way that a bit of the environment can be saved. But the concept of green marketing is much deeper. It is not only limited to customer concern but also encourages business houses to proper utilization of the resources such as -water consumption, usage of solar energy, usage of renewable materials, fuel-efficient methods, etc. Hence, green marketing can be seen as a weight balancing between commerciality and sustainability.

Focused upon how companies are opting for long-term eco-friendly products. The paper also describes the benefits of green marketing and various tools used by the companies for green marketing and its future challenges.

Methodology: The descriptive form of methodology is applied. Various research journals and websites are used to collect information.

Green Marketing Tools

Green marketing tool is used to produce environmentally friendly products and create awareness for green products among consumers and change customers' perceptions of the usage of green products. Such tools in general influences firms' policies and practices that affect the environmental quality and level of concern for the community.

Figure-1.1- Green Marketing Tools

1. Eco-Labeling: It is one of the most important tools of green marketing practiced around the world. Its main work is to identify those products and services that are environmentally friendly. Labels are made with small paper pieces with complicated diagrams, along with specific information regarding the product. In short, eco-labeling is mainly used as a part of the packaging. In many countries, proper eco-labeling is an obligatory law that has to be followed by the production houses. The labels are mostly concerned with agricultural products, energy conservation, hazardous metal-free electricals, non-toxic plastic packaging materials, recycled paper, and biodegradable cleaning agents. In another way, eco-labeling is also taken as a motivative factor for consumers to buy these green products. Through these labels, consumers also came to know about the materials used while production.

For example: BIS Eco-Mark is used as Eco-Label in India for various products related to FMCG (Fast Moving Consumer Goods) Industry, Electrical Industry, Plastic Goods, Cloth Industry, etc.

Green marketing belongs to that category of marketing, where environmental benefits are concerned when producing any form of products and services. The term green marketing was first discussed in the era of late 80s and early 90s when the first workshop on "Ecological Marketing" was organized in 1975 by the American Marketing Association (AMA). The main slogan of the workshop was sustainability in everyday activity. Presently, green marketing has accumulated in itself a wide spectrum ranging from eco-friendly products, sustainable business practices, eco-friendly packaging, and green marketing campaigns.

2. Eco-Branding: As we all know branding in general terms is a name, symbol, logo, design, or **Green Marketing Mix:**

The marketing mix can be described as marketing tools or strategies that combine several elements that solidify a product or service. The main aim of the green marketing mix is to reduce expenses, stick to social responsibility, and educate people about how environmentally friendly the company's offering can become. According to the

combination of all these to specify a product or service. This branding helps general customers to distinguish between products or service competitors. Similarly, eco-branding is also a symbol or image of services or products that are assumed to be environmentally safe and non-hazardous. Hence, recognition of brands while purchased by consumers is very critical. It is at this point that eco-branding works are required to educate customers those green products are also very useful and one step ahead compared to non-green products.

For Example, the Meat Industry has a serious adverse effect on the environment, specifically on animals. Therefore, the Los-Angeles based company called 'Beyond Meat' founded by Ethan Brown in 2009 is a revolution in eco-branding. This company produces delicious Plant-Based-Meat, which is, better for human health, the environment, climate change, and animals. The company 'Beyond Meat' uses green branding by combining cool graphics through which they try to show the benefits that how their product is saving the planet.

3. Environment Advertisement: To raise public awareness worldwide and to draw public attention regarding the purchase of green products, environmental advertisement is the more appropriate tool. These advertisements are done through media, e-newspapers, campaigns, and social media networks. The customers who feel responsible for the health of planet earth, as well as overall well-being, always show interest in the environment and human and animal rights.

For Example, 'The Body Shop International Limited' is a British Cosmetics, Skin Care, and Perfume Company; founded by Anita Roddick in 1976. The Company is also known for its campaign for green issues, even before the actual green marketing started. The company mainly focused on human rights and improved standards of human testing of cosmetics rather than animal testing.

four 'Ps' of green marketing, every element in the marketing mix should be green in its perspective. So basically, green marketing is all about the production, promotion, and distribution of green products or services along with customers concerned with the health of humankind and the earth at a large.

Hence, the four 'Ps' of green marketing are: -

Figure 1.2- Green Marketing Mix

(Source: FuiYeng. W & Yazdanifard. R, 2015).

Product: The product design and development should be through the recycled method and pollution-free. A company should take care that products should not be containing toxic substances For Example, FUJI XEROX, a joint venture between Rank Xerox Ltd. and Fuji Photo Film Co., Ltd., developed its Green Wrap Paper to be more eco-friendly.

Price: Pricing plays a very prominent role, as the customers are already willing to pay extra. The company should also take responsibility to provide the premium quality product in exchange for a high price. Consumers are ready to pay a high price compared to product design, appeal, taste, and preferences.

For Example, Plastic shopping bags are highly charged by some retail outlets to discourage its usages.

Promotion: Advertising of social products should contain special sales promotions. Ads should promote an organic lifestyle, slogans showcasing health benefits, and a corporate image of environmental responsibility.

For Example, as part of the philosophy, BODY SHOP co-promotes one or more eco- campaigns each year

Place: Place defines crucial importance as it mainly caters to companies' establishment and packaging technology. Here companies should give importance to marketing local and seasonal goods and services as it demonstrates fresh products and minimizes pollution due to logistics.

For Example, A reverse logistics system has been developed by FUJI XEROX to remanufacture copies. (Source: Kontic. I & Biljeskovic. J, 2010)

Green Marketing Practices

Today, many companies strive to be in the business world by becoming more environmentally responsible. Many companies are adopting the green methodology from the very beginning that is from

such as chromium, lead, aluminum, bismuth oxychloride, parabens, and any other harmful substances.

collecting the raw material to top management. Therefore, the ethical code of this century is 'Green' without any doubt. Companies today very need to be mindful not only of workers, customers, and shareholders but also of the environment and community it is established. Nowadays, even customers are also acknowledging green marketing gradually. Hence, companies are accountable to maintain customers' inclination toward green marketing is very essential. Since every product while getting produced involves more or less energy consumption and some amount of waste materials are being produced. Therefore, different companies participate in green marketing based on their company's ethics and green value. Some of the leading examples of green marketing practices are-

Ben and Jerry's Homemade Holding Inc an American Ice-Cream company found in 1978 in Burlington. It produces ice cream, frozen yogurt, and sorbet. The company promotes natural ingredients that promote the health of the earth due to its mission to reduce the greenhouse effect. It uses recyclable or biodegradable packaging materials.

Starbucks, a coffee shop is famous not only for its products but also for its promotion of sustainable coffee growing practices, premium salary to farmers, and education of the farmers for adoption of environmentally friendly practices.

Johnson and Johnson is an American multinational company founded in 1886 that produces pharmaceuticals and mainly baby products. Its low waste policy over the past 20 years is one of the famous working policies till now.

Green Toys Inc., a leading manufacturer of toys for

children. The company is very much concerned about the earth's health and children's rights. The company produces toys made with 100% recycled materials. The toys are mainly made up of recycled plastic jugs, packed with recycled materials and printed with soy ink.

Tata Motors Limited is one of the Indian Multinational Automotive manufacturers. The company along with its channel partner practices its 'Go-Green' initiative. Under this initiative, a sapling is planted after the sale of every new vehicle and for a new customer who gets their vehicle serviced at a company dealer workshop.

Wipro Eco-Energy is an electronic manufacturing company based in Karnataka, India. The company provides an intelligent and sustainable solution to its partner companies to reduce carbon footprints and energy wastage.

Yes Straws is a leading pioneering manufacturer of biodegradable consumer goods. It is co-founded by Arsentil Farenik in Ukraine. This company has taken the initiative to clean the plastic from sea beaches that causes harm to the environment and the death of aquatic animals. They manufacture eco-friendly straws which are 100% biodegradable, as goods are mainly made from wheat and cane stems.

Reliance Power a part of the reliance group is one of the leading private sectors in India. Reliance power always tried to uphold natural resources and reduce its environmental impact. They have 5 guiding principles for sustainable development - Reduce, Reuse, Recycle, Renew and Respect.

Seventh Generation is an American company that

3. It makes organizations realize that they too live on this planet and they have to be more environmentally responsible. In a way contributing positively towards earth health.
4. Companies create many green campaigns which in turn educate customers regarding the core meaning of living a green lifestyle.
5. Green marketing helps the multinationals to refocus upon the local and sessional products which in turn build a stronger relationship with the state government.
6. It helps to reduce carbon footprints and also saves natural resources thus heading to sustainable development
7. Green marketing also helps business houses to reposition their brands and stand out from other competitors in the market.
8. It helps companies to uplift their business status from regular to premium which creates space for further expansion and thus more profit in the long run.

Challenges Business Houses Face While Going Green:

Challenges are something which is faced by an individual or a company at a large while

3. **Green Myopia-** Myopia is a condition where

mainly produces cleaning papers and personal care products. The company innovated the production process with eco-friendly products which are toxic-free and also priced items are competitively lower than other green initiative companies' products.

Pela, is a Canadian company founded by Jeremy Lang. The company started with the production of biodegradable phone cases. They have a motto called technology for an everyday product without everyday waste. They use 60,000+ plastic phone cases which are thrown away every year and reuse them to produce 100% biodegradable sunglasses, smartwatch bands air pod cases, etc. All these products are also free from harmful elements like lead, cadmium, and phthalates.

Numi Organic Tea, is a social enterprise established in Canada known for its premium tea quality, fair trade, and sustainable practices of cultivation of various green, black, and white tea varieties. Its main mission is to extend holistic well-being to protect the planet earth. (Source: Sownie, C, 2021)

Benefits of Green Marketing:

Green marketing is the demand of today's business world. For humans to survive and maintain their existence green marketing is one of the mandatory steps to be adopted. Thus, analyzing its importance following benefits are described-

1. Green Marketing is an influential path to making a strong connection with consumers and as well as positioning the brand more strongly.
2. Green marketing helps companies to attract more audiences.

participating in a competitive situation. This competitive situation calls for more performance pressure in terms of ability and strength. Likewise, every kind of business also faces some form of challenges, so the same can be said for the business houses which are striving for green marketing. Thus, let's look at some of the biggest challenges faced by the business while practicing green marketing.

1. **Anti-Green Image-** The main problem comes when a company adopts a green mode of production and promotes the same, some of the competitors or consumers try to prove themselves that the company's product is anti-green. Such anti-green inclination leads to a negative image and loss of sales.

2. **A New Concept-** The concept of green marketing started in the era of 80s and 90s, still it is not clear within the market. Consumers only relate to green marketing as watching ads and buying green brands. Tons of people do not go for a healthier life style such as daily exercise or having a proper diet. Rather they only go on purchasing green products.

closer objects appear clear but the far-off

objects appear blurry. Marketing myopia means a focus on short-term selling ignoring the long-term vision. Similarly, green myopia refers to when a specific company's single product is green but does not pass consumers' satisfaction level as other products of the same company are not green and environmentally safe.

4. **Lack of Standardization**-Studies have depicted that marketing campaigns that claim to be adopted green marketing, do not explore the total truth about the product. Moreover, due to a lack of standardization, proper authentication cannot be done. Thus, in the absence of a proper quality check, green board, or association, there seems no way for the customers to know about the product is fully organic or regular. Ultimately, the loss of sales and customer belief. (Source: Qureshi. A, 2019)

Conclusion:

Comparing past decades today we can see and realize there is a total change in consumer

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preferences and business policies. Green marketing is expanding its influence bit by bit and with this many unknown challenges are also coming. Due to the shift from traditional to green marketing, both consumers and business houses are taking responsibility to maintain the earth's health. Hence, green marketing can be taken as a sharp tool that can protect the earth, and in addition, if applied in the right manner companies and also gain a competitive advantage.

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